

FOODITY News

Stories on food, data and digital innovation

Dear reader,

Over the past three years, we at FOODITY have supported a **diverse group of innovators across Europe working at the intersection of food, data, and citizen empowerment**. Through our Open Calls, **12 teams** have developed and tested digital solutions addressing real-world challenges; from personalised nutrition and food safety to sustainability, traceability, and food waste reduction.

In this edition, we spotlight all our **FOODITY innovators**, offering a brief overview of each project and inviting you to explore their work in more detail on their dedicated project pages.

Happy reading!

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Meet the FOODITY Innovators

3 FAIR

Open Call #2

3 FAIR (fair data, fair food, fair network) empowers fair-trade and

DIAITA

Open Call #1 (FOODITY Star Award Winner)

DIAITA provides science-based dietary recommendations to

ECOTRACE

Open Call #1

EcoTrace helps individuals make more sustainable food choices

solidarity food networks with digital tools that strengthen relationships between producers, retailers, and consumers. The project focuses on transparency, sustainability, and community-driven food systems.

[Learn more](#)

support patients, caregivers, and healthcare professionals. Using AI and evidence-based nutrition, the project promotes shared decision-making and personalised dietary support in healthcare contexts.

[Learn more](#)

through a data-driven app that combines nutrition insights, carbon footprint analysis, and data sovereignty principles. The project also focuses on educating users about food systems and data ethics.

[Learn more](#)

FOODMARKETMAP

Open Call #1

FoodMarketMap enhances the Eatvisor app with AI-driven components that support personalised nutrition and sustainable shopping. The solution helps citizens make healthier, more affordable food choices while respecting data privacy.

[Learn more](#)

MI4SAFERFOOD

Open Call #1

MI4SaferFOOD uses multispectral imaging to assess food safety and quality, particularly for fruits and vegetables. The project aims to improve consumer decision-making while building valuable datasets for food quality analysis.

[Learn more](#)

MYNUTRI

Open Call #2

MyNutri is an AI-powered mobile app that provides personalised health scores and carbon footprint insights for food products. Combining nutrition data with sustainability metrics, it enables more informed, responsible shopping decisions.

[Learn more](#)

ONCONOURISH

REDUCE

Open Call #2

SEBP

Open Call #2

ONCONOURISH

supports cancer patients with personalised, AI-powered nutritional guidance during treatment. By combining scientific expertise, technology, and patient-centred design, the project helps improve dietary adherence and quality of life.

[Learn more](#)

REDUCE tackles plate waste in canteens through AI-driven analysis and active user engagement. The solution provides catering companies with actionable insights to optimise operations and promote more sustainable dining practices.

[Learn more](#)

SEBP enables companies to offer sustainable products from local producers as employee benefits. The platform combines digital management tools with impact measurement to support responsible consumption and corporate sustainability goals.

[Learn more](#)

STRADA

Open Call #1

STRADA addresses food waste and safety by providing real-time spoilage data through smart technology. Its solution empowers individuals to make better food decisions while supporting healthier diets and reducing avoidable waste.

[Learn more](#)

THE KITCHEN ADVENTURE

Open Call #1

The Kitchen Adventure encourages healthier and more sustainable eating through a gamified cooking app. Developed with professional chefs, the solution combines AI, behaviour change techniques, and privacy-first design to build everyday cooking skills.

[Learn more](#)

TRACE-IT

Open Call #2

TRACE-IT improves food traceability by aligning regulatory requirements, industry needs, and consumer expectations. The project supports transparent, citizen-centred, and sustainable food supply chains across Europe and beyond.

[Learn more](#)

Success stories in food, data & innovation
from FOODITY & DRG4FOOD Innovators

A RECIPE FOR CHANGE

Download the FOODITY & DRG4FO Innovators Booklet

Take a deeper dive into the **20 data-driven food and nutrition innovations** supported by FOODITY & DRG4FOOD (our sister project) and explore how responsible digital solutions are shaping the future of food.

[Download the PDF](#)

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